

A Thank You Note – to Professor Nina Thornhill

Stratos Pistikopoulos*

**Artie McFerrin Department of Chemical Engineering, Texas A&M University,
College Station, Texas, USA (e-mail: stratos@tamu.edu).*

Abstract: Stratos Pistikopoulos is the TEES Eminent Professor and the director of the Energy Institute at Texas A&M University. He is the Editor-in-Chief of Computers and Chemical Engineering. Stratos is an alumnus of Ignacio Grossman. From 1991-2015 he was Professor of Chemical Engineering at Imperial College London and was elected Fellow of the Royal Academy of Engineering in 2013.

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I have had the pleasure of knowing Professor Nina Thornhill throughout my academic career from my early days at Imperial College and the Centre for Process Systems Engineering [CPSE] while she was still at UCL. I had also the distinct pleasure to welcome Nina at Imperial from UCL when I was CPSE's Director.

She has always been an integral member of and played pivotal role in the success story of CPSE throughout the years – through her research work, her active involvement in the operation of the Centre and her mentorship, friendship and words of wisdom. Jointly, we were involved in a number of European activities together in the field of control [see for example Ref 1 below]. I have also had the opportunity to collaborate with her in the area of operational and maintenance planning [see References 2 & 3].

There are two unique characteristics of Nina's that in my opinion stand out and for which we all feel very privileged to be associated with her:

1. Her research stamp in the field and the impact within CPSE and the community through her work on 'data analytics' – in an environment where first-principle modeling has been the 'bread-and-butter' and major force of thinking. Her work stood out – and in retrospective, she has been a pioneer in greatly advocating the emerging need to 'listen to the data' and make intelligence use of them.
2. Her gentle and smooth personality, approaching people always with smile, care and humility, a great listener - always showing a breadth and depth of a very

charismatic scholar and individual. In the contemporary era, in academia and elsewhere, where big egos dominate the agenda, Nina's approach to life, academia, research and beyond have shown to us that that academic excellence does not necessary equate with 'academic arrogance'.

Thank you Nina - wishing you all the best for the future.

Stratos

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